

D5.5 Communications activity reports

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

TASK 5.1

Summary

Task description:

This task focused on communicating the project objectives and results to a wide range of external stakeholders throughout the project and on seeking input to the project from stakeholders. The communications processes adopted will utilise a range of tools including developing a dedicated project website, printed communication materials, videos, articles and papers at conferences and in the media (online and print media). The deliverable will analyse the results of these activities.

Results and conclusion:

A plan of communication and an analysis of the communication of each Thematic Networks were released to provide relevant communication activities.

As planned, the communication reached the EURAKNOS partners, the Thematic Networks partners, the EIP-AGRI community and all the agricultural community.

We managed to adapt our communication to the crisis thanks to virtual meeting, workshops and conferences.

Deliverable Number	Work Package
D5.5	WP5
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Planned Delivery Date	Actual Delivery Date
31/03/2021	31/08/2021

Type of Deliverable	R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	X
	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	
	E	Ethics	

Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

AKIS - Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
 EG – Explorer’s Guide
 EIP-AGRI – European Inn
 ESIF – European Structural Investment Funds
 EU – European Union
 EURAKNOS – Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs: towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open-Source System
 EUREKA – European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices
 GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation
 H2020 – Horizon 2020
 HIKR – High Impact Knowledge Reservoir
 IP – Intellectual Property
 KIP – Knowledge Innovation Panel

 KPI – Key Performance Indicator
 KR – Knowledge Reservoir

MAA – Multi Actors Approach
NGO – Non-Governmental Organization
OG – Operational Group
PA – Practice Abstracts
SIB – Strategic Innovation Board
SME – Small and Medium Enterprises
T – Task
TN – Thematic Network
WP – Work Package

1. Introduction

This deliverable outlines the communication activities conducted over the course of the EURAKNOS project.

1.1. Context

EURAKNOS (www.euraknos.eu/) is a Thematic Network (TN) created with the aim to collate knowledge from all TNs to build a single community. TNs have the potential to maximise the uptake and impact of new knowledge by stimulating shared learning and coordinating the dissemination of practical information. The overall aim of the EURAKNOS project is to strengthen the EU agricultural knowledge base by co-creating “the network to connect all thematic networks”.

Communication requires engagement with policy makers, at both European and regional/national levels, as well as the research and knowledge transfer communities and farmers, advisors, and industry to ensure that outputs can be exploited by all actors at the European, regional or national level.

The communication is important in EURAKNOS because the project aims to reinforce the EU agricultural knowledge base by building the blueprint for a data system to enable the farming/rural community with an easier access to best practices from all EU H2020 Thematic Networks. It is impossible to gather so many Thematic Networks and other publics without a good communication.

Moreover, the communication, to reach as many publics as possible, should be through different channels like social media, physical or digital cross visits, videos and podcasts, workshops... This diversity is the possibility to engage different actors, to let them meet and communicate between them about specific subjects, to reach people with who we do not have a connection with. It is essential for a relevant exchange of knowledge.

This report will emphasise the strong and weak points of the communication in the EURAKNOS projects concerning the channels we used as well as the publics we targeted.

1.2. Objectives

The main objectives of EURAKNOS are to:

- Develop technical guidelines for building a successful TN based on the multi-actor approach
- Define best dissemination practices (tools, materials, channels...) with high impact on the end-users in particular farmers, foresters and advisors.
- To develop a pilot for an open-access EU wide agricultural knowledge innovation system.

To achieve these objectives, EURAKNOS will:

- Facilitate and support TNs, link similar initiatives at EU and national levels and feed into national educational and training programmes;
- Widen and connect existing TNs to build knowledge reservoirs within the agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI);
- Collect, evaluate and compare knowledge, materials and tools that have been produced by TNs and operational groups (OGs);
- Develop a harmonised approach by producing technical guidelines on how to make a high-impact knowledge reservoir;
- Develop a blueprint for creating an EU-wide, dynamic, open-source agricultural knowledge innovation database, and explore the value of doing this.

The aim of Work Package 5 in EURAKNOS was to communicate and to widen and maximise the impact of the outcomes of EURAKNOS through dedicated communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. The specific objectives of WP5 were:

- to develop a detailed and dynamic communication plan.
- to progress a detailed and dynamic dissemination plan and exploitation plan.
- to efficiently communicate on the concept, progress, and the results of EURAKNOS to a wide variety of stakeholders.
- to fastidiously disseminate of EURAKNOS outputs targeted to the actors with a focus on two groups of end users, on the one hand, TN coordinators as multipliers and on the other hand the farmers, foresters, and advisors.
- to provide a wide range of targeted end-users material.
- to link to educational programs and training initiatives.
- to promote cross exchange between different TNs.

To achieve these objectives, WP5 was focused on 4 distinct but inter-related tasks: T5.1 Communication activities, T5.2 Dissemination and Exploitation, T5.3 Networking, and T5.4 Cross-exchange. Together, these tasks fostered engagement with policy makers at European (EU) and regional/national levels; the research and knowledge transfer (KT) community; and farmers/foresters, advisors, and industry. Communication activities have raised awareness of the project.

2. Task members

In this table, you will find the partners involved in each task of the WP5. In bold, are the task leaders of each task.

Table 1. Partners involved in the different Tasks of WP5

Task	Partner														
	ACTA	IDELE	NAK	UGent	GLZ	USC	AU	PSKW	ARC	AUA	IFA	LFG	RAU	EV ILVO	IFOAM
5.1	X	X	X			X					X		X		
5.2	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
5.3		X	X		X	X	X	X			X		X		
5.4	X	X	X		X			X	X		X		X		X

IFOAM was not originally planned to be a partner of task 5.4 but they contributed and got the budget to do it.

3. Methodology

Each partner was invited to list their “communication activities” in a dedicated table. The table was available in the project’s SharePoint.

In the first sheet of the table, the partners had to write the type of communication, the channel of communication, a description of their communication activities, the main audiences reached, who led the activity, the name of the event, the place of the event, the date of the event and the other contributors.

In the second sheet of the table, digital communication, the partners had to write approximatively the same information: the type of online communication activities, description of online including social media activities, main audiences, the lead, the web-link, the place, the date, the contributors. This table was used for the social media, the newsletters, the website etc.

Thanks to this sheet, it was possible to monitor the number of communication activities the partners have been involved in and assess whether partners have reached the KPI and know which partners participated in the activities and which ones did in a lesser extent. The table also allowed us to know how many and what kind of people were targeted by our activities.

Nevertheless, precaution must be taken with the table since it is sometimes difficult to know the exact number and the work background of each participant to an event.

This communication activities report is also based on the D5.1-Plan of Communication. The communication activities report should answer to the plan of communication, it helps to know if the planned objectives were achieved. Nevertheless, we can observe discrepancies between both documents: the absence of translation of the website and of social media. The translations in nine languages were planned in the plan of communication but translations have not been done since it would have taken time and money the project did not have. We can observe that the time needed for communication is often underestimated in regard to its importance. Moreover, translating all the documents of a website is not an easy task. Some partners may have needed the assistance of a professional translator. To be able to respect the plan of communication, each partner should have been engaged in the translation of the documents, for the website it was complicated. Nevertheless, it should have been done for the social media since every partner has the capacity to write short publications every week about the project in its own language.

4. Content / results

4.1. Communication activities

During the EURAKNOS project, several communication activities were planned such as workshops, workgroups, consortium meetings and a final conference. EURAKNOS partners also participated to other events to represent the project.

* Workshops

EURAKNOS members organized three workshops, one in Budapest, one in Paris, and one online.

In Budapest, a 2-days workshop on KR TN impact assessment was organized for the coordinators of all TNs (Euraknos TNs + other TNs) and linked OGs when possible and KIP to present and discuss the work performed in the tasks, to exchange experiences and know how between the different TNs and to come up with quantitative and qualitative criteria as a basis for the creation of the High Impact Knowledge Reservoir. In total 26 consortium members and 32 members of the Knowledge Innovation Panel (KIP) have attended the workshop.

In Paris, a 2-day workshop presenting the High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR) was organized for the coordinators of all TNs and linked OGs when possible and KIP and SIB to present and discuss the work performed, integrate the vision paper and to come up with HIKR (TN) technical guidelines for a harmonized approach. The Explorer's Guide have been translated in 12 EU-languages. To have a shared and global agreement on the proposed guideline, this task was performed with a co-design and multi-actor approach.

The third workshop was online, and it was divided in four sessions.

During the first session, there was an introduction to the EURAKNOS TN and the aim of the workshop and the TN Explorer's Guide, the methodology of the workshops, and an explanation of the programme. It gathered 48 participants, of which 21 were from EURAKNOS. Other participants included 3 advisors, 4 consultants, 3 farmers, 1 IT-professional, 1 policymaker, 15 researchers.

The second session was about the roles of different actors in the Multi Actor Approach in Thematic Networks. 39 participants attended the webinar, of which 22 were from EURAKNOS. Other participants included 2 advisors, 4 consultants, 2 policymakers, 9 researchers.

The third session was about assessing end-user needs and identifying the best ways to harvest and co-generate user-friendly knowledge. 36 participants attended the webinar, of which 16 were from EURAKNOS. Other participants included 3 advisors, 2 consultants, 1 farmer, 1 IT-professional, 1 policymaker, 11 researchers, 1 SME; from 8 participants the background could not be identified.

The last session was about designing end-user engagement strategy. 35 participants attended the webinar, of which 17 were from EURAKNOS. Other participants included 3 advisors, 2 consultant, 2 policymakers, and 11 researchers.

The workshops have been a way to reach and gather commercial farmers, foresters, agriculture advisory services, companies, NGOs, basic, oriented & applied research organisations, regional policy makers & ESIF managing authorities and National Rural Networks.

* Workgroups

During the above workshops, 12 workgroups took place and managed to gather a total of 654 participants. The repartition is represented in the figure below. We can see that most of the participants belong to an undefined category, indeed it was difficult to classify the origin of the participants. A lot of them also belong to the scientific community.

Figure 1- Number of participants to a workgroup per category

* Consortium meetings

During the project, EURAKNOS organized 5 consortium meetings, one meeting was organized every six months. The first three meetings were in presential, and the last ones were online because of the Covid situation. Only members of the consortium, among them the SIB and the KIP, were conveyed since the consortium meetings are intern communication and confidential.

* Final conferences

Two final conferences took place online the 5th and the 26th of February 2021.

The event of the 5th of February was divided in three sessions and gathered more than 50 persons per session. Project coordinator Pieter Spanoghe from Ghent University introduced the background of this EU-funded project, which worked to keep the European thematic networks alive, serving farmers, foresters, and advisors in the long term, supported by a Strategic Innovation Board & a Knowledge and Innovation Panel representing the agricultural society in Europe.

It started with the presentation of the Thematic Network Explorer's guide, a key output that gathers the experience from all TNs on how to set up successful projects. After that, the EURAKNOS Vision Paper & policy recommendations were presented. The vision described a centralised, EU-wide, open-source digital platform to share and store practical knowledge outputs from TNs on agriculture and forestry topics. Policy recommendations were related to three areas: digital systems, practical outputs, and reach & networking.

Finally, the development of the EURAKNOS platform/prototype was presented. EURAKNOS has established a proof of concept and provided valuable lessons and experiences. The work on the platform does not end with the project but will continue with its sister project, EUREKA, also

coordinated by Ghent University. Going forward in EUREKA, testing of the minimum viable product is key, as is working in an iterative and sequential as well as flexible and agile way. The EUREKA team is generating and integrating feedback from end users to improve the design of the platform, ensuring usability and the inclusion of all features needed, connecting back-end to front-end.

The second event, on the 26th of February, gathered 109 participants, around 50 attended per session. During one session, the tool Mentimeter was used to know the work background of the participants. We can see on the figure below that most of them were from the research field and in the advisory field.

What is your daily work background?

Figure 2- Work background of the participants of the final conference

Here are the links to watch the three sessions:

Session 1 for the general public - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6sT9Nb5yTr4&t=4s>

During this session, EURAKNOS partners presented what we have achieved and how to use it : the website, the practice abstracts, the factsheets, the platform that is currently developed with EUREKA and the explorer’s guide with a MAA approach. After that, an interactive session about the MAA took place.

Session 2 for the European projects’ community - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=X7coYzS2t1w&t=1285s>

During this session, the partners presented a reflection on workshops, showcase podcasts and PAs. After that, an overview of the EG was presented with a focus on MAA – value of involving target users and how to include them in projects. Then, the partners presented the platform, mention IP/licensing agreements, metadata, and the FAIR principles. Finally, the sustainability of EURAKNOS thanks to EUREKA was presented.

Session 3 for the policy makers - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ex6_zb_Wiz4

During this last session, the partners presented the Key recommendations and ideas from EG with a policy perspective, they presented the platform with a focus on value at EU-level and its link to EUREKA. Finally, there was an interactive discussion about “how to facilitate the policy recommendations?”.

* Participation to events

EURAKNOS partners reported their participation in 24 events of communication: conferences, workshops and activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects. Among them, 20 were online and 4 were physical. The diversity of the public reached is very important, we can notice, in the table below, a predominance of the advisers/ researchers since 1758 people were reached, and of the scientific community since 495 people were reached in this category. In total, 2981 people have been in contact with EURAKNOS's partners during a communication event.

Figure 3- Number of people reached by the EURAKNOS community per category

4.2. Digital communication

4.2.1. Social Media

EURAKNOS aimed to be very present on Social Media. It is a way to be in contact with people belonging to the network of the project. It is also a way to invite people to give their opinion and contact us. Social media have the advantage to be seen all around Europe at any time. EURAKNOS publishes on Twitter, Facebook, Linked In and Instagram so that they can reach different publics.

* EURAKNOS Twitter account

We mainly used the social media Twitter since it is the most used by the Thematic Networks and our other stakeholders. This social media is useful to share information about the events that are organized by the partners, to publish information about our deliverables and to share information published by the other thematic networks or partners. The interactions with the community are easy via Twitter. EURAKNOS account currently has 509 followers and 608 tweets and retweets. The Twitter account can be viewed at: <https://twitter.com/euraknos>

Figure 4- Twitter page

Among the 602 tweets and retweets, 196 posts were tweeted from the EURAKNOS account and 406 posts were retweeted from accounts belonging to our partners and the participants of the project. In May 2020, a communication table was created to give the responsibility of social media to a different partner each week. This strategy was efficient since we can see in the figure below that the partners have published more from this moment and that the number of impressions also increased.

Figure 5- Number of posts tweeted from EURAKNOS Twitter account and number of impressions by month

In the communication plan, delivered in month 3, the expectations for the Twitter account were to reach EURAKNOS’s partners, TN’s partners, EIP-AGRI actors and the agricultural society. After analysing the followers from Twitter, we can see that these targets have been reached.

Figure 6- Number of followers per category

* EURAKNOS Linked In account

The EURAKNOS Linked In account is followed by 228 persons, it was created in March 2020 and it is our second main mean of communication. Until now, we published 48 publications, which represents around 4 publications per month but were not regular. Here is the access to our Linked In account: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/euraknos>

On the figure below, you can see the evolution of our number of publications in one year. We notice that in February 2021, a lot of publications were posted. This is due to the high number of events that happened that month.

Nevertheless, some partners also published about the EURAKNOS project from their account, the partners published 25 publications that potentially reached 7673 people, but we do not have more indications on this public.

Figure 7- Evolution of the number of publications on Linked In

The number of impressions has also evolved a lot since the creation of the page. It is certainly related to the number of our publications because we can see the number of impressions has been higher since November 2020.

Figure 8- Evolution of the number of impressions

The people who liked the page are mainly from the scientific community, from the industry or are researchers/advisers. You can see the repartition in the figure below.

Figure 9- Number of followers on Linked In per category

* EURAKNOS Facebook page

We also used a lot the social media Facebook. 200 persons currently follow the Facebook page and we have published 118 posts since the creation of this page which means around one publication per week since the beginning of the project even though it has not been very regular. Here is the link to our Facebook page: <https://www.facebook.com/euraknos/>. You can find the evolution of our number of publications in the figure below.

Figure 10- Number of publications on Facebook per month

Moreover, some partners also published about EURAKNOS on the Facebook of their organization, a total of 28 publications about EURAKNOS were made and potentially reached 34 627 people but we do not have more specific information about these posts.

* Instagram

Finally, EURAKNOS also has an Instagram account. After one year of utilisation, we did realize that we did not reach an interesting public. Our publications did not have enough impact. We managed to reach 162 followers and we published 33 photos but after that, we preferred focusing our efforts on more impacting social media. Our last publication on this account was the 30th of January 2020.

Figure 11- Pictures of the EURAKNOS Instagram account

4.2.2. Video and music platforms

* Spotify

During the EURAKNOS project, the partners recorded 50 podcasts and uploaded them on our Spotify Channel. The tool is very interesting because it allows the persons to listen to the podcast while doing something else. Nevertheless, someone who does not have a Spotify account cannot listen to the podcasts, only extracts, so we also uploaded the podcasts on You Tube.

Figure 12- View of the Spotify Channel

Among the 50 podcasts, 25 podcasts were focused on communication and our ‘network of thematic networks’ – we offered a platform to other TNs. The other 25 podcasts were focused on dissemination – explaining the work carried out and findings from EURAKNOS.

Among the listeners, 370 people started to listen to the podcast, 210 people streamed the podcast and 73 people properly listened to the podcasts. It makes a total amount of 653 people going to our Spotify Channel. Moreover, the podcasts were also published on YouTube.

* YouTube Channel

To complete the possibility of listening to the podcasts on Spotify, we uploaded them on our YouTube Channel so that people who do not want to create a Spotify account still could listen to the podcasts. On the YouTube account, there are also videos of presentation of our deliverables, and webinars. 55 videos have been uploaded on the channel.

Almost every video was uploaded in October 2020 or after. It can explain the 21 subscribers to our channel even if we can also explain it by the fact that professionals do not usually subscribe to YouTube Channels. We have had 1.571 views of our videos since the creation of the Channel in October 2019, and we can notice that the number of views change a lot from a video to another. Our videos of presentations of the deliverables (platform and Explorer’s guide) have a lot of success whereas our podcasts have less, which is normal since we usually communicate on our Spotify Channel for the podcasts.

Figure 13 - EURAKNOS YouTube Channel

Discussion:

We can observe that videos that have received views and like are the ones that have been promoted. Most of the videos were uploaded on YouTube six months before the end of the project because we realized it would be an interesting mean of communication. Nevertheless, a special communication should have been created around each video, like “one week, one video” to have more views on each. Basically, podcasts were not very popular whereas video of promotion were really appreciated since we communicated more about them.

Moreover, the impact of the podcasts has not been sufficient: Among the listeners, 370 people started to listen to the podcast, 210 people streamed the podcast and 73 people properly listened to the

podcasts. It makes a total amount of 653 people going to our Spotify Channel. The creation of these podcast took a lot of time and it would have been useful to do a specific communication on each thanks to the social media and the partners who would have published these podcasts on the website of their organization. It has not been done but it would have probably increased the number of listeners. Moreover, among the 50 podcasts, 25 podcasts were focused on communication and our ‘network of thematic networks’ – we offered a platform to other TNs. The other 25 podcasts were focused on dissemination – explaining the work carried out and findings from EURAKNOS. So, it should have reached different publics, it should have interested many people. Podcasts were interesting but maybe some of them were too specific. In future projects, if podcasts are done, there must have an important communication about it, otherwise the time spend to produce podcasts is too long for almost no impact. The same comments can be made for videos on YouTube, each partner should communicate about them on the main social media page but also in each language. For future projects, videos should be uploaded one by one with a specific communication for each. A strict timetable should be established, followed and controlled.

4.2.3. Newsletters

EURAKNOS sent 19 newsletters during these 27 months in 10 languages: English, French, Spanish, Italian, Hungarian, Greek, Danish, Dutch, Estonian and German, which means a total of 190 newsletters, adapted to our readers from many places in Europe. We currently have 447 subscribers, and the newsletters are available on the website: <https://euraknos.eu/news>

18th newsletter

Dear readers,
 First of all, the EURAKNOS team wishes you a Happy New Year in 2021.
 The end of EURAKNOS is coming very soon but we still have a lot to share with you. In this newsletter, we will inform you about:
 * The Farmbook: From EURAKNOS to EUREKA
 * Raiders of the lost Agricultural Knowledge : What did you miss ?
 * The final conference: "From EURAKNOS to the EUREKA of European Knowledge Exchange"
 * The importance of EURAKNOS Practice Abstracts
 * The EURAKNOS Policy Brief
 Please [subscribe to the EUREKA newsletter](#) to follow-up the work that will continue beyond EURAKNOS.
 Enjoy your reading,
 The EURAKNOS team

The Farmbook: From EURAKNOS to EUREKA

Developing a platform which gives access to a knowledge reservoir is not an easy task and requires a large amount of work in order to be able to collect different types of content in the back-end and present it in the front-end. In EURAKNOS a proof of concept and visuals for the future platform were developed in order to detect the potential difficulties encountered on a small scale when creating such a platform for 8 Thematic Networks.
 Subsequently, the EUREKA project used the gained knowledge in order to scale up the scope of the platform to Multi-Actor Projects within the H2020 research and innovation program and create a prototype and Minimum Viable Product. This will allow the Farmbook to be tested by end users and collect feedback on how to further improve the platform in the future.

Figure 14- EURAKNOS newsletter

Raiders of the lost Agricultural Knowledge, what did you miss ?

On Friday 5th of February, the event took place by Zoom and gathered more than 50 persons per session. Project coordinator Pieter Spanoghe Ghent University introduced the background of this EU-funded project, which works to keep the European thematic networks alive, serving farmers, foresters, and advisors in the long term, supported by a Strategic Innovation Board & a Knowledge and Innovation Panel representing the agricultural society in Europe.

It started with the presentation of the [Thematic Network Explorer's guide](#), a key output that gathers the experience from all TNs on how to set up successful projects.

After that, the EURAKNOS [Vision Paper](#) & [policy recommendations](#) were presented. The vision described a centralised, EU-wide, open-source digital platform to share and store practical knowledge outputs from TNs on agriculture and forestry topics. Policy recommendations were related to three areas: digital systems, practical outputs, and reach & networking.

Finally, the development of the EURAKNOS platform/prototype was presented. EURAKNOS has established a proof of concept and provided valuable lessons and experiences. The work on the platform does not end with the project but will continue with sister project EUREKA, also coordinated by Ghent University. Going forward in EUREKA, testing of the minimum viable product is key, as is working in an iterative and sequential as well as flexible and agile way. The EUREKA team is generating and integrating feedback from end users to improve the design of the platform, ensuring usability and the inclusion of all features needed, connecting back-end to front-end.

If you missed this event you can catch it on [webinar](#) or if you would like to know more about our outputs, you should attend our [final meeting on Friday, February 26th](#).

Final Conference "From EURAKNOS to the EUREKA of European Knowledge Exchange"

The success of the newsletter has increased with time. At the beginning, barely 40 people used to open the newsletter whereas now, between 140 and 160 read it. According to the analytics, the average percentage of subscribers who often open and click on the newsletter is 24%; the proportion of our subscribers who sometimes open our newsletters and click on it is 27%; finally, 48% of our subscribers rarely open and click on our newsletters.

The people who read our newsletter the more often are located in Budapest (Hungary); Paris (France) and Athens (Greece)

Figure 15- Number of readers per newsletter

The newsletter is the best way for us to reach our public from the thematic networks and the advisers. It is really spread, and people seem to take the time to read it.

4.2.4. Website

EURAKNOS website is also useful for the communication on the project. It has a great importance since it is the first element people look for on internet. The website has the interest of being more sustainable than the social media and the newsletters. The website will be maintained for 5 years and after that, the resources will be transferred to the Farmbook, the platform currently developed by the EUREKA project.

The EURAKNOS website was viewed by 17.018 persons since its creation. According to the figure below, most people have seen the main page. Nevertheless, there are also many people who have seen the page “about” with the most important information about the project, the page “thematic networks” that gathers links to many thematic networks, the page “deliverable” where you can find the reports, the podcasts, the videos, the translations of the explorer’s guide etc. Finally, many visitors saw the page “news” which gathers the latest news like the newsletters.

Figure 16- Number of viewers per page of the website

Moreover, the page counts 4.466 users, these people click on the articles/ sections of the website. Among them, 1.975 people found the website by an organic search on Internet, 1.774 people were redirected to the website; 780 were redirected by our newsletters and similar documents and 244 discovered the page thanks to our social media. We can see on the figure below that among the 244 people who discovered the website, half of them discovered the EURAKNOS website thanks to Twitter, our most efficient social media. Furthermore, around 30% of the people who discovered the EURKNOS website via social media did it by Facebook whereas it looked like Linked In was more efficient than Facebook.

Figure 17- Number of people who discovered the website via the social media

We can conclude with the idea that the website, the newsletters, and the social media together are a good combination since the newsletters and the social media help to communicate and reach people whereas website store the information for interested people.

Furthermore, some shortcomings and suggestions on these activities must be explained:

- Communication activities such as translation, dates of publication, creation of a national page etc should have been written more specifically to get the partners responsible. Each country should have had a national page to raise the awareness of national actors like in other projects. Once again, the language is the main barrier, and a bigger budget should have been planned.
- A work of sensibilisation to the communication should have been realized among the partners of the project at the beginning. Several of the partners do not see this activity as something important for the project but more as something accessory they do when they have a moment. We should have decided to name a communication officer per organisation to reduce workload for maintaining active communication by each partner. Moreover, a more important budget should have been given to this activity since it is very important for the future of the project.
- In addition, there should have been more relation between social media and events, workshops etc. On social media, we could have done more advertisement about the events, do more lives during the event and capitalise more after these events with pictures, testimonies etc.

All these elements were pointed out in the analysis of the thematic networks we did in deliverable D2.3. Nevertheless, the DoA and the budget were decided during the setting up phase of the project, not after this analysis. For future projects, this analysis should be presented to partners writing a proposal to build a thematic network.

4.3. Impact indicators and results

This section is dedicated to the results the EURAKNOS partners reached during the project according to the target groups and the impact indicators decided in the communication plan.

Table 2- Impact Indicators and results of the communication activities

Communication activities	Specific target groups	Impact indicators	Results
Participation to events	Level I: TNs partners, AKIS community, researchers, end-users, policy makers	up to 250 people reached by participating	The EURAKNOS partners have participated to 24 events. During these events, they have been in contact with 2981 people. The aim was to reach 250 people, we can easily imagine that 1/10 of the people in contact with the EURAKNOS partners during the events have been interested in EURAKNOS. Among these 2981 people, 1750 are researchers and advises, moreover 495 are part of the scientific community which includes the AKIS community, finally 235 policy makers were also there. We can conclude from this information that we reached the targets we planned to reach.
5 Consortium meetings	Level I & II: EURAKNOS partners, KIP, SIB	up to 60 participants	Five consortium meeting were organized during the projects. 3 in presential and the other ones online due to the COVID situation. The people present were members of the consortium, including the KIP and the SIB. There were between 20 and 30 participants each time.
2 Workshops	Level I & II: TNs partners, linked OGs, and the Knowledge Innovation Panel	up to 70 participants (40 external)	Three workshops were organized, in Budapest, in Paris and online. In total 26 consortium members and 32 members of the Knowledge Innovation Panel (KIP) have attended the first workshop. The second workshop was not for a big number of people but for the TN coordinators. The third one reached people from the TNs partners, the linked OGs and the KIP. The workshops did not gather 70 people at the same time which is too much to build a real and efficient work together. They gathered between 35 and 48 people at each sessions, all with their own background to enrich the conversations.
4 Workgroups	Level I & II: TNs partners, linked OGs, and the Knowledge Innovation Panel	Up to 100 participants (60 external)	During the workshops, 12 workgroups were organized and gathered 654 participants in total. Most of the participants belong to an undefined category, indeed it was difficult to classify the origin of the participants. A lot of them, 208 people, also belong to the scientific community which covers the TNs partners, linked OGs, and the Knowledge Innovation Panel.

1 Final conference	Level I, II, III, IV: AKIS community, researchers, endusers, policy makers and education	Up to 150 participants	<p>Two final conferences, held as webinars, were organized on the 5th of February and on the 26th of February 2021.</p> <p>The event of the 5th of February gathered 150 people and the event of the 26th gathered 109 people which makes a total of 259 people.</p> <p>According to the Mentimeter we used during one of our sessions to know the origin of our participants, many of them were from University, Researcher, Academic, Advisory organisation, farmers association, etc.</p>
1 website	Level I, II, III, IV: AKIS community, researchers, endusers, policy makers and education	Up to 10.000 visitors	<p>A website was created at the beginning of the project: https://www.euraknos.eu/</p> <p>The website has been visited 17.018 times. It was also used by 4.466 people who discovered the page by the newsletters, the social media and by looking for it specifically, so we reached the expected targets.</p>
1 Twitter account	Level I, II, III, IV: AKIS community, researchers, endusers, policy makers and education	Up to 500 followers	<p>A Twitter account was created at the beginning of the project: https://twitter.com/euraknos</p> <p>The Twitter account is followed by 506 people who are mainly from the scientific community, from H2020 projects and researchers.</p>
1 Facebook account	Level I, II, III, IV: AKIS community, researchers, endusers, policy makers and education	Up to 200 followers	<p>A Facebook page was created at the beginning of the project: https://www.facebook.com/euraknos/</p> <p>200 people currently follow the EURAKNOS Facebook page.</p>
1 Instagram account	Level I, II, III, IV: AKIS community, researchers, endusers, policy makers and education	Up to 200 followers	<p>An Instagram account was created at the beginning of the project:</p> <p>https://www.instagram.com/euraknos/?hl=fr</p> <p>162 people liked the page. We did not try to have more followers because we stopped the page after the first year of the project.</p>
1 Linked In account	Level I, II, III, IV: AKIS community, researchers, endusers, policy	Up to 200 followers	<p>A Linked In page was created at the beginning of the project:</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/company/euraknos</p> <p>229 persons currently liked the page. Half are from the scientific community and the others are mainly researchers and industrials. This fits with our objectives.</p>

	makers and education		
1 You Tube account	Level I, II, III, IV: AKIS community, researchers, endusers, policy makers and education	Up to 200 followers	<p>A You Tube page was created at the beginning of the project: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCTOvLzwYhftUffZ8JFDg2bg</p> <p>We have 21 subscribers to our page. This is a small number, but many people don't have a You Tube account and just watch the videos. We have had 1.571 views of our videos since the creation of the page in October 2019 reaching a very large community of actors.</p>
Up to 100 abstract sheets	Level I, II, III, IV: AKIS community, researchers, endusers, policy makers and education	up to 800 people outreached by promotional materials	100 practice abstracts have been published
Up to 50 podcasts	Level I, II, III, IV: AKIS community, researchers, endusers, policy makers and education	up to 500 people outreached	<p>We created and uploaded 50 podcasts on Spotify, You Tube and the website. https://open.spotify.com/search/euraknos</p> <p>653 people went to our Spotify platform to listen to our podcasts. Moreover, our podcasts are on You Tube and have been viewed 432 times on this channel.</p> <p>Then, in total, our podcasts outreached 1085 people.</p>
5 videos	Level I, II, III, IV: AKIS community, researchers, endusers, policy makers and education	up to 150 people outreached	<p>5 videos were released:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Building a digital knowledge database to collect outputs from various Thematic Network Projects – 106 views : https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1HeToAEdtAw&t=2s -Introducing the EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks – 165 views: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xxV1YFADA7I -Best Practices for Thematic Networks According to Past and Present Projects – 175 views: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vB4usFzC6zg&t=13s

			<p>-What can EURAKNOS offer Thematic Network Projects? – 243 views: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BmrGyF2ViO0&t=18s</p> <p>-EURAKNOS Workshop Budapest – 294 views : https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OLcB90NnRNw&t=11s</p> <p>Only our most recent video is under 150 views, it could be because it is the most recent one so people have had less time to watch it. Moreover, the videos of the webinars are also available on the EURAKNOS You Tube Channel.</p>
Up to 25 pres-releases and newsletters	Level I, II, III, IV: AKIS community, researchers, endusers, policy makers and education	Up to 2.000 people reached by each newsletter	<p>EURAKNOS sent 19 newsletters during these 27 months in 10 languages: English, French, Spanish, Italian, Hungarian, Greek, Danish, Dutch, Estonian and German, which means a total of 190 newsletters. They were sent to 447 subscribers but the average number of readers per newsletter was 108.</p> <p>We reached much less persons that we expected because of the GDPR rules that prevented us to create our own list of diffusion from our networks. The project was submitted before this rule so we did not plan this aspect.</p>
1 Vision Paper	Level III: EU Commission , policy makers, TNs	up to 200 people reached	<p>A Vision Paper was released and was presented on the website, the social media and during the conferences. Several partners promoted it in social media/newsletters so we should have reached >200 persons. It was also translated to Estonian to reach as many people as possible : http://www.acta.asso.fr/fileadmin/ressources/Europe/EURAKNOS_Vision_Paper.pdf</p>
Policy Brief	Level III: EU Commission , AKIS, policy makers, TNs	up to 200 people reached	<p>A Policy Brief was released: https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/EURAKNOS-Policy-Brief.pdf</p> <p>The policy brief was published in the Open Access Project Repository Journal in January 2021. This publication was distributed free of charge, digitally, to circa 150,000 people across Europe (plus a second distribution of circa 70,000 covering North America, China and Japan). Total distribution was therefore circa 220,000 globally. Subscribers include people in the European Commission, Government agencies and departments throughout Europe, America and Asia, Municipalities, local and central government</p>

			departments including some Ministries responsible for education, climate, agriculture, environment, defence etc, European funding agencies and Research Councils, Universities, research centres, Institutes, labs, Associations, Academia, Global NCP's, NGO's, project co-ordinators (Policy-Funding-Science).
1 bible	Level II, III: AKIS community, researchers	up to 200 people reached	<p>The bible of EURAKNOS is the Explorer's guide: https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/Explorers-guide-EN-interactive.pdf</p> <p>It was translated in French, Spanish, German, Italian, Danish, Hungarian, Romanian, Slovenian, Nederland, Greek, Lithuanian, and Estonian to be read and used by as many people as possible.</p>

These KPI were defined during the setting up phase of the project but were not discussed during the negotiation phase of the Grant Agreement, therefore accepted by the European Commission. Nevertheless, we accept the criticism and offer a reflection on the relevance of these KPIs.

Part of the KPI were not precise enough or coherent

First KPI for dissemination, KPI for networking and KPI for communication were not well separated, these activities were mixed during the project as well, it showed a difficulty to distinguish the 3 activities.

KPI should have been better reflected in relation with the activities planned in the WP.

- There is no KPI related to the social media, the website or YouTube/Spotify
- There is a KPI on the number of OGs involved, but involving them has not been very successful, the consortium should have built more links with OGs during the whole project duration in order to help the transfer of knowledge.
- KPIs were not precise enough – We could not treat all of them. For example:
 - o Number of policy makers reached through vision paper 10 (per country) ; 280 (in Europe), 20 (globally)
 - o Farmers and foresters reached yearly through the widening of the TNs 500 (per country), 14 000 (in Europe)

These numbers were not well defined and were not realistic. It seems very complicated to know for example if a policy maker was reached by the vision paper or another deliverable (since the vision paper came out the last months of the project), it is also difficult to know which year was reached a farmer and be sure this number was reached each year. Finally, it is complicated to know if these KPIs were targeting communication, dissemination, networking, a little bit of the three etc. In future projects, there should be a more precise work of definitions of the KPIs during the setting up phase of the project.

Moreover, a second table of the KPI did not have target value at all but just a list of outputs to characterize end user needs, then it is complicated to know if we answer to what was expected or not. In this table, the only elements that have a number to reach are:

- 150 high impact abstract sheets/ infographics, 5 videos, 50 podcasts and 30 cross thematic newsletters for commercial farmers, foresters and representative organisations
- 150 high impact abstract sheets/ infographics, 5 videos, 50 podcasts and 30 cross thematic newsletters for Agriculture advisory services

Nevertheless, nothing indicates if these are the same documents or if it has to be planned differently for each public.

It would have been relevant to create three tables of KPI: dissemination, communication, networking, in three different sheets in the same Excel table, and to explain and separate clearly dissemination, communication and networking. Keeping everything in the same document with explanation and clearly defined KPI would have help a lot. A simple system to fill after each event or publication on internet would have helped the partners to realize a better quantitative analysis. Moreover, someone could have been in charge to send them a reminder each two month to ask them to fill the document all along the project lifetime.

5. Conclusion

We can consider that the EURAKNOS communication has been efficient: we reached almost every KPI, we reached a great diversity of public, used many tools and channels to have an adapted approach to each target. The communication was a priority of EURAKNOS and that's why we managed to reach our indicators.

As the other thematic networks, we faced some problems to find a rhythm to publish on the social media, we realized some tools were not as efficient as we thought and imagined new ways of communicating during the course of the project. Sometimes, we also had the problem of mobilizing partners around communication but after the first projects' months and by adapting the responsibilities, they have been more active. Finally, it is complicated to quantify people we reached thanks to our activities of communication. However, our deep qualitative analysis show EURAKNOS' impact. Indeed, results produced by the project reached our expected targets. Future projects should think about th problematic of quantifying impact since the very beginning of the project when starting the first communication activities and even during the setting up phase of the project.

There are also good practices in the communication of EURAKNOS that could be reused in other projects. The communication table giving responsibilities for social media to a different partner each week was a very good initiative since people have been more involved and aware of what was happening. Since its creation in May 2020, the number of articles published, and audience reached has been higher.

Moreover, the translation of the newsletters in the different languages of the project was also a good opportunity because it allows local people to get informed about EURAKNOS activities, it removes one of the most important barriers in European countries.

Finally, there was a good synergy between the channels to reach (social media and newsletters) and the website where the information is. Future projects should also create a lot of links between these media, it harmonizes the communication.

Nevertheless, some shortcomings and difficulties must be underlined:

- The change from physical to virtual events made difficult to evaluate the impact, the difference of public. Moreover, the events were renamed so it made the evaluation complicated.

- There has been a lack of translations. Only the newsletters and a few deliverables were translated. In this kind of project, a more important budget should have been allocated to the translation of the documents to raise the awareness of people of several countries even when they do not speak English. Moreover, national pages of the project should have been created on social media since we know that it is the most effective mean of communication to reach a broad audience.
- A document should have been strictly filled and checked after each communication activity to know who the public was, what kind of event, what kind of post. Such a document existed but has not been followed enough. Picking every piece of information at the end of the project was difficult to reach the necessary level of precision.

6. Next steps

EUREKA created a communication following the same strategy and advises we did in our analysis of the communication of the Thematic Networks. There are synergies between EURAKNOS and EUREKA logos, websites, and styles.

The content of the two projects will be added to the Farmbook once it is ready to ensure the sustainability of the projects.

7. References

The following documents were useful to write the Communications activity reports:

- Grant Agreement number 817863 -
- Policy Brief: <https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/EURAKNOS-Policy-Brief.pdf>
- Vision Paper: http://www.acta.asso.fr/fileadmin/ressources/Europe/EURAKNOS_Vision_Paper.pdf
- Explorer's Guide: <https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/Explorers-guide-EN-interactive.pdf>
- EURAKNOS Newsletters: <https://euraknos.eu/news>
- EURAKNOS website: <https://euraknos.eu/>
- Analytics tools of Google, Facebook, Linked In, Twitter, You Tube and Spotify
- Reports of the workshops
- Reports of the events
- Reports of the meetings
- Communication activities table
- Analysis of the communication of the TNs:
https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/D3.3_20200430_Report_on_HIKR_strategies_to_D_C.pdf

